

Improving Perceptions of Maternal Respectful Care Among Black Women

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Background

Risk of pregnancy-related death in U.S. for Black women is 3-4 times greater than White women. In addition, Black women have 2-3 times the adjusted risk for severe maternal morbidity which includes obstetric hemorrhage, hypertension disorders of pregnancy, maternal sepsis, and cardiac complications.

Problem

- More than half of the Severe Maternal Morbidity (SMM) cases are **preventable** and may be influenced by lack of **respectful maternity care (RMC)**
- Studies involving perinatal providers identified increased maternal risk among Black Women due to **failure to listen or lack of response** to patient's expressions of concern

Purpose

The purpose of this DNP project was:

1. To develop and implement an educational program for perinatal nurses adapted from the Association of Women's Health, Obstetric and Neonatal Nurses RMC framework to promote patient-centered communication
2. To evaluate the program's impact on Black birthing women's perspectives of RMC using pre- and post-intervention survey data

Methods

- **Design:** Quality Improvement (QI) Project
- **Participants:** Postpartum patients and Perinatal Nurses
- **Setting:** Acute Care Children's & Women's Hospital
- **Measures:** RN module completion and intervention compliance rates; comparison of baseline and post-intervention Patient Reported Experience Measures (PREM) and Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (HCAHPS) survey data

The Iowa Model of Evidenced-Based Practice Framework

Identify Trigger	Gaps in birth outcomes of Black women and their newborns continue despite statewide efforts to improve overall maternal morbidity and mortality
State the Question	What affect will a Respectful Maternity Care program for perinatal nurses have on Black women's perception of their care during their birthing experience?
Form a Team	Project Coordinator, BirthCare Center leadership team, Physicians, and representatives from Quality, Risk Management, Spiritual Care and Human Resources
Synthesize Evidence	Review of Literature Analysis of baseline HCAHPS & RMC perception data
Pilot Change	Staff training and their commitment to and implementation of RMC behaviors Established RMC Champion role and training
Integrate & Sustain Change	Monitored Process and Balancing measures Reinforcement of practice change (i.e., RMC champion activities)
Disseminate Results	Facility project team and staff (e.g., unit display of RMC commitments and behaviors) Continued participation in AWHONN National project

Results

HCAHPS Survey

■ Pre-Data collected March-July 2022 ■ Post-Data collected Aug-December 2022

PREM Survey

Discussion

- Limited number of Black women responded to baseline and post-intervention HCAHPS (17 and 13) and PREM (11 and 5) surveys
- Slightly increased HCAHPS (6.5%) and PREM (2%-22% in 8 of 9 items) survey scores
- Outcomes indicate Respectful Maternal Care may positively impact Black birthing patient's perception of respectful care
- Nurses are in an optimal position to honor and assure Black women's concerns are heard during their birth experience
- Caregivers sitting with patients help to promote mutual respect and understanding, which can provide an emotionally safe space
- Adoption of Respectful Maternal Care behaviors promotes shared decision-making, evidence-based care
- RMC promotes adoption of advocacy efforts by nurses actively listening to understand and respond with empathy to individual patient needs

Limitations/Recommendations

- Small sample of eligible discharged Black women participated in both PREM and HCAHPS surveys during baseline and post-intervention data collection
- Significant nursing staff turnover during project implementation resulting in need for continued training of new nurses and travelers
- PREM survey has not undergone validity and reliability testing
- HCAHPS response rate of 11.2% is below the national average of 26%
- Additional research is needed to determine if RMC behaviors decrease clinical outcome disparities for Black birthing women

References

